

“Exposure Assessment in Furan”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

Author: Demetris Kafouris

Email: dkafouris@sgl.moh.gov.cy

Organisation: State General Laboratory

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1 Summary

Furan is a heterocyclic organic compound, consisting of a five-membered aromatic ring containing four carbon atoms and one oxygen atom. Furan is found naturally in food products that have been processed in high temperatures and in the presence of carbohydrates, ascorbic acid, and/or fat. Furan is also considered toxic and potentially carcinogenic.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.5.4. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary furan intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the furan exposure.

Mean dietary furan exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.111 and 0.403 µg/kg b.w. per day for mean and high consumers, respectively. Current exposure levels of Cypriot population are not of health concern with regards to carcinogenicity. There was no significant difference in furan intake between genders and different geographical areas.

Coffee beverages (84.7%) were the highest contributor to furan intake for adult populations while for younger population processed infant and children food were the food categories with the highest contribution to furan intake.

2 Introduction

Furan is a colorless, flammable, and highly volatile liquid with a boiling point close to room temperature. It's a heterocyclic organic compound, consisting of a five-membered aromatic ring containing four carbon atoms and one oxygen atom. Furan is used as a starting material in the synthesis of various organic compounds and also serves as a solvent in some chemical reactions. Additionally, it's found naturally in roasted coffee and in some other foods. However, it's also considered toxic and potentially carcinogenic.

Dietary exposure to furan occurs mainly through the consumption of certain foods and beverages. Furan can form during the cooking or processing of certain foods, especially those high in carbohydrates, ascorbic acid, and/or fat, when exposed to high temperatures.

Foods and beverages that may contain furan include coffee, canned food, processed food, and alcoholic beverages. Furan is naturally present in roasted coffee beans. The levels of furan in coffee can increase during the brewing process, particularly when using methods involving high temperatures such as espresso or percolation. Furan can form in canned foods, particularly those containing vegetables, fruit juices, or baby foods, during the heat treatment process used for sterilization. Certain processed foods, such as baked goods, especially those containing fats, ascorbic acid, or added sugars, may contain furan due to the heating processes involved in their production. Furan can also be found in alcoholic beverages, particularly those that are aged or contain added fruits.

Regulatory agencies around the world monitor furan levels in food and beverages and set limits to reduce human exposure. To minimize dietary exposure to furan, it's recommended to avoid overcooking or burning foods, store foods properly to prevent spoilage, consume a varied diet with a balance of fresh and minimally processed foods, limit the consumption of heavily processed foods and beverages, and follow cooking recommendations to minimize the formation of furan during food preparation.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary furan intake of the population in Cyprus, to carry out the necessary risk characterization and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the furan exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Furan occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2022. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOD were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario and LOD

for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset contained 65 food items.

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset contained 82921 occasions.

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 14.3 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Furan summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.5.4

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Furan
Substance Category	Contaminant
Value	1310 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference	Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Furan

Scenario				
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	
Min	0	0	0	
Max	1.456	1.46	1.464	
Mean	0.109	0.111	0.111	
95% C.I.	(0.095 - 0.123)	(0.096 - 0.124)	(0.096 - 0.124)	
SD	0.152	0.152	0.152	
P25	0.010	0.011	0.012	
Median	0.043	0.043	0.043	
P75	0.148	0.149	0.149	
P95	0.403	0.403	0.403	
MoE (Mean)	11991	11938	11887	
MoE (P95)	3254	3253	3252	

* MoE:Margin of Exposure

Mean and 95th percentile exposure was calculated as 0.111 and 0.403 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day (Table 4.2). The above values are lower than the corresponding exposure estimates, calculated by EFSA. MOEs for carcinogenicity (BMDL of 1310 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day) obtained for the current exposure to furan (Table 4.2) were above 10000, which is considered a safety margin for no health concern.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
FEMALE	0	1.460	0.112	(0.09 - 0.134)	0.170	0.009	0.040	0.140	0.468	11715	2801
MALE	0	1.161	0.108	(0.091 - 0.124)	0.131	0.012	0.056	0.165	0.367	12180	3571

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Mean Furan exposure across Gender

MB scenario

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
Ammochostos	0	1.161	0.102	(0.048 - 0.156)	0.166	0.011	0.054	0.108	0.430	12823	3049
Lamaka	0	0.928	0.111	(0.077 - 0.146)	0.170	0.016	0.039	0.137	0.518	11775	2530
Lefkosia	0	0.722	0.117	(0.096 - 0.138)	0.137	0.018	0.064	0.178	0.378	11220	3469
Lemesos	0	1.368	0.116	(0.086 - 0.146)	0.163	0.007	0.042	0.165	0.526	11297	2492
Pafos	0	1.460	0.080	(0.049 - 0.11)	0.122	0.003	0.017	0.117	0.316	16459	4147

Mean Furan exposure across Area MB scenario

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	95% C.I.	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	MoE (Mean)	MoE (P95)
Adolescents	0	0.626	0.048	(0.036 - 0.06)	0.101	0.001	0.007	0.032	0.265	27148	4937
Adults	0	0.928	0.133	(0.113 - 0.152)	0.164	0.018	0.076	0.185	0.453	9857	2890
Elderly	0	0.521	0.095	(0.082 - 0.108)	0.108	0.019	0.059	0.135	0.338	13777	3875
Infants	0	1.368	0.056	(0.041 - 0.071)	0.124	0.000	0.013	0.062	0.239	23279	5484
Other children	0	0.713	0.028	(0.02 - 0.036)	0.069	0.001	0.009	0.026	0.113	47235	11543
Toddlers	0	1.460	0.070	(0.037 - 0.066)	0.126	0.007	0.024	0.05	0.165	25438	7923

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that adults and elderly had higher exposure because of their high consumption of coffee beverages, since coffee is a high contaminated food category. Infants had also high exposure due to their low body weight and the consumption of processed cereal baby food. On the other hand, other children had the lowest exposure since they do not consume food with high amount of furans. In all population classes the health risk of the current intake level was acceptable with the exception of adults, where the calculated MoE was on the limit of 10000.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to furan by population class and geographical area. It was found that in some population classes there may be a difference between the geographical areas. In general, the exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the foodstuffs that are contaminated by furan are consumed by all population classes in all geographical areas.

Mean Furan exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total furan exposure is shown in Figures 4.7 and 4.8. For infants the highest contribution to the furan intake was processed cereal baby food (24.3%), followed by other processed ready to eat baby food (3-8 %) (Figure 4.7). In the case of adults, the main contributor to furan exposure was coffee with 84.7% (Figure 4.8).

Contribution to the Furan Total Exposure (MB) -Infants-

Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Furan Total Exposure MB (infants).

Contribution to the Furan Total Exposure (MB)
 -Adults-
 Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Figure 4.8: Contribution to the Furan Total Exposure MB (adults).

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Furan Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 3 with greater than 1% contribution

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Coffee beverages	3	Adults	77.03%
Coffee beverages	3	ALL	70.16%
Coffee beverages	3	Elderly	56.39%
Coffee beverages	3	Adolescents	47.72%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Coffee ingredients	3	Elderly	30.90%
Cocoa beverages	3	Other children	28.16%
Vegetable juices	3	Other children	27.13%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	3	Infants	24.25%
Cocoa beverages	3	Adolescents	22.48%
Vegetable juices	3	Toddlers	17.36%
Coffee ingredients	3	Adults	17.03%
Coffee ingredients	3	ALL	16.74%
Chips, crisps, fries and dough-based analogues	3	Other children	15.35%
Ready-to-eat dairy-based meal for children	3	Toddlers	14.53%
Ready-to-eat mixed meal for children	3	Infants	13.65%
Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	3	Infants	13.16%
Vegetable puree or paste	3	Infants	12.67%
Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	3	Toddlers	11.64%
Ready-to-eat mixed meal for children	3	Toddlers	10.84%
Tea beverages	3	Toddlers	9.89%
Tea beverages	3	Infants	8.54%
Tea beverages	3	Adolescents	8.32%
Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	Infants	8.04%
Tea beverages	3	Other children	7.84%
Coffee beverages	3	Other children	7.29%
Tea beverages	3	Elderly	6.75%
Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	3	Toddlers	6.46%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Coffee ingredients	3	Adolescents	6.16%
Cocoa beverages	3	Toddlers	5.99%
Vegetable juices	3	Adolescents	5.98%
Ready-to-eat dairy-based meal for children	3	Infants	5.24%
Mixed juices with added ingredients	3	Other children	4.48%
Follow-on formulae	3	Infants	4.29%
Chips, crisps, fries and dough-based analogues	3	Adolescents	3.47%
Tea beverages	3	ALL	3.43%
Ready-to-eat cereal-based meal for children	3	Toddlers	3.33%
Snacks other than chips and similar	3	Toddlers	3.29%
Follow-on formulae	3	Toddlers	3.29%
Vegetable juices	3	Infants	3.18%
Vegetable juices	3	Elderly	3.08%
Vegetable juices	3	ALL	3.04%
Ready-to-eat vegetable-based meal for children	3	Infants	2.69%
Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	Other children	2.65%
Snacks other than chips and similar	3	Other children	2.63%
Chips, crisps, fries and dough-based analogues	3	Toddlers	2.60%
Tea beverages	3	Adults	2.50%
Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	Toddlers	2.48%
Mixed juices with added ingredients	3	Toddlers	2.11%
Infant formulae	3	Infants	2.08%
Cocoa beverages	3	ALL	2.05%
Vegetable juices	3	Adults	1.73%
Biscuits, rusks and cookies for children	3	Toddlers	1.62%

Food category	Food level	Population class	Contribution to Total exposure
Snacks other than chips and similar	3	Adolescents	1.46%
Biscuits, rusks and cookies for children	3	Infants	1.34%
Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	Toddlers	1.33%
Cocoa beverages	3	Elderly	1.29%
Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	Adolescents	1.22%
Mixed juices with added ingredients	3	Adolescents	1.10%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of furan has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the aggregation of occurrence data	+/-
Use of the substitution method for non-detects	+/-
Use of weight coefficients for non-representativeness of the population	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹+ = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure;
- = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as furan concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with a GC-MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumptions taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary furan exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 0.111 and 0.403 µg/kg b.w. per day for mean and high consumers, respectively. The above values are lower than the corresponding exposure estimates, calculated by EFSA. MOEs for carcinogenicity (BMDL of 1310 µg/Kg b.w. per day) obtained for the current exposure to furan were above 10000, which is considered a safety margin for no health concern.

There was no significant difference in furan intake between genders and different geographical areas.

For infants the highest contribution to the furan intake was processed cereal baby food (24.3%), followed by other processed ready to eat baby food (3-8 %). In the case of adults, the main contributor to furan exposure was coffee with 84.7%.

7 References

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3. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.
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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices